

A Study of Thinking Styles and its Impact on Life Skills among Secondary School Students

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ABSTRACT

There is an much difference in the thinking pattern and the styles of human. It often relevantly changing with the genders, locality, schools and the environments. The life style also has its own impact on the thinking style. In school, the Variety of the students comes from the different places, schools, language, economics and social status, these all may influence or certainly not sometimes. The motivation taken for the present study to the employ statistical techniques by using SPSS package to showcase the frequency and percentage differences in the level of Thinking Styles and Thinking Styles among secondary students were found using statistical deviation. T-test and F-test was carried out for finding the significant differences present in the demographic variables.

KEYWORDS: Motivation, Life skills, school students, thinking style

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According to david kolb's theory, learning is a four-step process that includes concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization and active experimentation. this position represents two dimensions: concrete experience versus abstract thinking, and reflective observation to active experimentation. these dimensions include four learning styles: divergent, convergent, assimilate, and accommodate. according to kolb and ferry, the learner needs four different abilities to function efficiently learning styles involve several variables such as academic performance of learner, higher education improvement; critical thinking and problem solving due to the importance of learning styles and critical thinking in students' academic performance, a large volume of educational research has been devoted to these issues in different countries.

Demirhan, Besoluk and Onder (2011) in their study on critical thinking and students' academic performance from the first semester to two years later have found that contrary to expectations the students' critical thinking level reduced but the total mean of students' scores increased. this is due to the fact that the students are likely to increase adaptive behavior with environment and university and reduce the stress during their education .

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study as follows

INTRODUCTION

The current world needs people with a lot of capabilities such as understanding and using different ways of thinking, research, problem solving, critical thinking and creativity. critical thinking is one of the aspects of thinking that has been accepted as a way to overcome the difficulties and to facilitate the access to information in life . In addition to critical thinking, learning style, i.e. the information processing method, of the learners, is an important key factor that has a major role in problem solving.

General objective

- To find out the thinking styles and its impact on thinking styles among secondary school students in Coimbatore district.
- To adopt questionnaire on thinking styles and its impact on thinking styles among secondary school students

Specific objectives

- To find out the level of thinking style of secondary school students.
- To find out the impact of thinking styles among secondary school students.
- To find out the impact of independent variables like gender, locality, medium of study, type of school, parents educational qualification.

VARIABLES USED

in research, this term refers to the measurable characteristics, qualities, traits, or attributes of a particular individual, object or situation being studied. researchers use the term variable whether they are conducting, reading or using results of qualitative or quantitative research. researchers often refer to variables by the terms dependent or independent. dependent variables represent outcomes of interest, and they are affected by independent (i.e predictor) variables. in this study the investigator will follow independent variables and dependent variables.

- Independent variables
- Dependent variables

Independent variables

Also, the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender
- Medium of study
- Location of the school

- Type of school
- Parents education

Dependent variables

Thinking styles and thinking styles as dependent variables.

DATA COLLECTION

The data was collected using a questionnaire, the study is based on primary data which was collected from a sample of 250 secondary school students in government and private schools in and around Coimbatore district. prior to the collection of data, the investigator got the permission from the school authorities. The data was collected from the selected samples by using questionnaire. totally the data was collected in 20 days. after the data collection, the investigator has employed the SPSS for analyze.

TABLE 1 LIST OF SCHOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTED

S. NO	SCHOOL NAME
1	SRI LATHANGI VIDHYA MANDIR MATRICULATION HR SEC SCHOOL
2	MARIYAMMAL GIRLS HR SEC SCHOOL
3	GOVT GIRLS HR SEC SCHOOL
4	AROKIYA MADHA MATRICULATION HR SEC SCHOOL
5	MUNICIPAL BOYS HR SEC SCHOOL
6	VISWADEEPI MATRICULATION HR SEC SCHOOL
7	PKD MATRIC HR SEC SCHOOL

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

HYPOTHESIS: 1

There is no significant mean score difference in thinking styles between the groups based on gender.

Table 2 – frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the thinking styles among secondary students based on gender.

GENDER	LOW		MODERATE		HIGH		TOTAL
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
MALE	0	0	20	80	5	20	25
FEMALE	0	0	130	57.78	95	42.22	225

From the table 2, that aimed the male students, 20% of them have high level and the of them moderate level of thinking styles. similarly, amid the female students, 42.22% of them have high level and of them have moderate level

TABLE -Significant mean score difference between thinking styles among secondary students with respect to gender.

GENDER	NUMBER	MEAN	S.D	DF	"T" VALUE	P VALUE	REMARKS
MALE	25	31.88	2.5972	248	0.0147	0.9883	NOT SIGNIFICANT
FEMALE	225	31.0756	2.52				

From the table 3, the calculated value(0.0147) is less than the table value of 't' the hypothesis 1 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of thinking styles among secondary students with respect to gender.

HYPOTHESIS: 2

There Is No Significant Mean Score Difference in The Thinking Styles Among Secondary Students Based on Locality

Table 4- Frequency and Percentage Difference in The Level of Mean Score Difference In The Thinking Styles Among Secondary Students Based On Locality

LOCALITY	LOW		MODERATE		HIGH		TOTAL
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
URBAN	0	0	62	73.80	22	26.20	84
RURAL	0	0	98	59.90	68	40.10	166

From the table 4 that amid the urban area students, 26.20% of them have high level and 73.80% the of them moderate level of thinking styles. similarly, amid the rural area students 40.10%, of them have high level and 59.90% of them have moderate level.

TABLE 5 Significant Mean Score Difference Between Thinking Styles Among Secondary Students With Respect To Locality

GENDER	NUMBER	MEAN	S.D	DF	"T" VALUE	P VALUE	REMARKS
URBAN	84	31.2738	2.5605	248	0.0034	0.9973	NOT SIGNIFICANT
RURAL	166	31.094	2.5323				

From the table 5, the calculated value(0.0034) is less than the table value of 't' the hypothesis 2 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of thinking styles among secondary students with respect to locality.

HYPOTHESIS: 3

There Is No Significant Mean Score Difference In The Thinking Styles Among Secondary Students Based On The Medium Of School.

Table 6- Frequency and Percentage Difference In The Level Of Mean Score Difference In The Thinking Styles Among Secondary Students Based On Medium Of School.

MEDIUM OF SCHOOL.	LOW		MODERATE		HIGH		TOTAL
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
TAMIL	0	0	49	77.78	14	22.22	63
ENGLISH	0	0	99	52.94	88	47.06	187

From the table 6 that amid the Tamil medium students,22.22% of them have high level and 77.78% the of them moderate level of thinking styles. similarly amid English medium students, 47.06% of them have high level and 52.94% of them have moderate level.

TABLE 7 SIGNIFICANT MEAN SCORE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THINKING STYLES AMONG SECONDARY STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO MEDIUM OF SCHOOL.

MEDIUM OF SCHOOL.	NUMBER	MEAN	S.D	DF	"T" VALUE	P VALUE	REMARKS
TAMIL	63	31.2698	3.0211	248	0.1924	0.8476	NOT SIGNIFICANT
ENGLISH	187	31.158	2.3604				

From the table 7 the calculated value(0.1924) is less than the table value of 't' the hypothesis 3 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of general qualification among secondary students with respect to medium of school.

HYPOTHESIS: 4

There is no significant mean score difference in the thinking styles among secondary students based on type of school.

TABLE 8- Score Difference Towards Thinking Styles Among Secondary Students Based On The Type Of School.

VARIABLE	TYPE OF SCHOOL	N	MEAN	STD.DEVIATION
THINKING STYLES AND VALUE EDUCATION	BOYS	17	30.5294	2.6596
	GIRLS	32	31.3125	2.1130
	COEDUCATION	201	31.1841	2.5877
	TOTAL	250	31.1560	2.5432

from the table 8 it is concluded that the mean value of boys 30.52 is whereas girls is 31.31,and the co-education is 31.18 and the others is 31.15 the result inferred that the mean value of co-education students is high compare to others.

TABLE 9 'F' RATIO BETWEEN THINKING STYLES AMONG SECONDARY STUDENTS WITH RESPECT TO THE TYPE OF SCHOOL.

TYPE OF SCHOOL	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.	RESULT
BETWEEN GROUP	7.617	2	3.8085	0.5845	0.5582	NOT SIGNIFICANT
WITHIN GROUP	109.299	247	6.5154			

From the table 9 the calculated value of "f" (0.5845) is less than the table value of 'f' which hold , the hypothesis 4 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards thinking styles among secondary students with respect to the type of school.

HYPOTHESIS: 5

There is no significant mean score difference in thinking styles between the groups based on parents educational qualification.

TABLE 10- Score difference towards thinking styles among secondary students based on the parents educational qualification

VARIABLE	EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF PARENTS	NO	MEAN	STD.DEVIATION
SCORE DIFFERENCE TOWARDS THINKING STYLE	ILLITERATE	40	30.75	2.81
	SCHOOL	59	31.22	2.71
	GRADUATE	151	31.24	2.39
	TOTAL	250	31.16	2.54

From the table 10, it is concluded that the mean value of illiterate is 30.75 whereas school is 31.22, and the graduate is 31.24 the result inferred that the mean value of graduate is high compare to others.

TABLE 11 'F' ratio between thinking styles among secondary students with respect to the parents educational qualification

SUBJECT	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.	RESULT
BETWEEN GROUP	7.86	2	3.93	0.6036	0.5476	NOT SIGNIFICANT
WITHIN GROUP	1609.05	247	6.51			

From the table 11 the calculated value of "f" (0.6036) is less than the table value of 'f' which hold, the hypothesis 5 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards thinking styles among secondary students with respect to parents educational qualification.

HYPOTHESIS: 6

There is no significant mean score difference in the life skill among secondary students based on gender.

TABLE 12 – Frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the life skill among secondary students based on gender.

GENDER	LOW		MODERATE		HIGH		TOTAL
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
MALE	0	0	20	80	5	20	25
FEMALE	0	0	130	57.78	95	42.22	225

From the table 12 that aimed the male 20% students, of them have high level and 80% the of them moderate level of life skill. similarly, amid the 42.22% of female students, 57.78% of them have high level and of them have moderate level.

TABLE 13 Significant mean score difference between life skill among secondary students with respect to gender.

GENDER	NUMBER	MEAN	S.D	DF	'T' VALUE	P VALUE	REMARKS
MALE	25	56.52	4.3185	248	0.1787	0.8583	NOT SIGNIFICANT
FEMALE	225	56.68	4.1457				

From the table 13 the calculated value(0.1787) is less than the table value of 't' the hypothesis 6 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of life skill among secondary students with respect to gender.

HYPOTHESIS: 7

There is no significant mean score difference in the life skill among secondary students based on locality.

TABLE 14- Frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the life skill among secondary students based on locality.

LOCALITY	LOW		MODERATE		HIGH		TOTAL
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
URBAN	0	0	62	73.80	22	26.20	84
RURAL	0	0	98	59.90	68	40.10	166

From the table 14 that amid the urban area students, 26.20% of them have high level and 73.80% the of them moderate level of life skill. similarly amid the rural area students, 40.10% of them have high level and 59.90% of them have moderate level.

TABLE 15 Significant mean score difference between life skill among secondary students with respect to locality.

GENDER	NUMBER	MEAN	S.D	DF	'T' VALUE	P VALUE	REMARKS
URBAN	84	56.9762	4.3177	248	0.5242	0.6006	NOT SIGNIFICANT
RURAL	166	56.5060	4.1008				

from the table 15 the calculated value(0.5242) is less than the table value of 't' the hypothesis 7 is accepted. . it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of life skill among secondary students with respect to locality.

HYPOTHESIS: 8

There is no significant mean score difference in the life skill secondary students based on medium of study.

TABLE 16- frequency and percentage difference in the level of mean score difference in the life skill among secondary students based on medium of study.

MEDIUM OF STUDY	LOW		MODERATE		HIGH		TOTAL
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
TAMIL	0	0	49	77.78	14	22.22	63
ENGLISH	0	0	99	52.94	88	47.06	187

from the table 16 that amid the Tamil medium students,22.22% of them have high level and the 77.78%of them moderate level of life skills. similarly amid English medium students, 47.06%of them have high level and 52.94% of them have moderate level.

TABLE 17 Significant mean score difference between life skill among secondary students with respect to medium of study.

MEDIUM OF SCHOOL	NUMBER	MEAN	S.D	DF	"T" VALUE	P VALUE	REMARKS
TAMIL	63	56.8254	3.9823	248	0.2408	0.8099	NOT SIGNIFICANT
ENGLISH	187	56.6096	4.2161				

From the table 17 the calculated value(0.2408) is less than the table value of 't' the hypothesis 8 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of life skill among secondary students with respect to medium of study.

HYPOTHESIS: 9

There is no significant mean score difference in the life skill among secondary students based on type of school.

TABLE 18- Score difference towards life skill among secondary students based on type of school.

VARIABLE	TYPE OF SCHOOL	N	MEAN	STD.DEVIATION
SCORE DIFFERENCE TOWARDS LIFE SKILLS	BOYS	17	57.353	4.123
	GIRLS	32	56.125	3.871
	COEDUCATION	201	56.692	4.216
	TOTAL	250	56.664	4.181

From the table 18, it is concluded that the mean value of boys is 57.353whereas girls is 56.125,and the co-education is 56.692. the result inferred that the mean value of co-education students is high compare to others.

TABLE 19 'F' ratio between life skill among secondary students with respect to the type of school.

TYPE OF SCHOOL	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.	RESULT
BETWEEN GROUP	17.518	2	2.759	0.4971	0.6089	NOT SIGNIFICANT
WITHIN GROUP	4352.258	247	17.62			

From the table 19 the calculated value of "f" (0.4971) is less than the table value of "f" which hold , the hypothesis 9 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards life skill secondary students with respect to the type of school.

HYPOTHESIS: 10

There is no significant mean score difference in the life skill among secondary students based on parents educational qualification.

TABLE 20 Score difference towards life skill among secondary students based on the parents educational qualification.

VARIABLE	EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF PARENTS	NO	MEAN	STD.DEVIATION
LIFE SKILLS AND VALUE EDUCATION	ILLITERATE	40	57.08	4.66
	SCHOOL	59	56.83	4.02
	GRADUATE	151	56.49	4.09
	TOTAL	250	56.66	4.24

From the table 20 it is concluded that the mean value of illiterate is 57.08 whereas school is 56.83 ,and the graduate is 56.49. the result inferred that the mean value of illiterate is high compare to others.

TABLE 21 'F' ratio between life skill among secondary students with respect to the parents educational qualification.

SUBJECT	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG.	RESULT
BETWEEN GROUP	12.97	2	6.48	0.3675	0.6928	NOT SIGNIFICANT
WITHIN GROUP	4356.82	247	17.64			

From the table 21 the calculated value of "F" (0.3675) is less than the table value of 'F' which hold , the hypothesis 10 is accepted. it is inferred from the above table that there is no significant mean score difference towards life skill among secondary students with respect to parents educational qualification.

CONCLUSION

It is found that there is no significant difference in the Life skills and Life skills among higher secondary students shall be encouraged to give more importance to Life skills and Life skills The above findings are an original contribution to the existing knowledge and no such studies have been attempted in these selected dimensions. This study might enable students o look for ways of enhancing social adjustment among higher secondary students and its impact of their academic achievement in Coimbatore District.

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APPENDIX-I
QUESTIONNAIRE
PERSONAL DATA SHEET AND QUESTIONNAIRE

DEAR STUDENTS,
GREETINGS! KINDLY REAL ALL THE STATEMENTS GIVEN IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE AND RESPOND TO THEM CAREFULLY. PLEASE FILL OUT THE PERSONAL SHEET. YOUR RESPONSE WILL BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL AND USED ONLY FOR MY M.ED., DISSERTATION.

MY DISSERTATION TOPIC IS "LIFE SKILL AND ITS IMPACT ON LIFE SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS"
THANKING YOU,

YOURS FAITHFULLY,
N.MAHARAJAN

GENERAL INFORMATION

NAME :
CLASS :
NAME OF THE SCHOOL :
GENDER : MALE / FEMALE
LOCALITY : URBAN / RURAL
MEDIUM OF STUDY : TAMIL / ENGLISH
TYPE OF SCHOOL : BOYS/ GIRLS/ CO-EDUCATION
PARENTS EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION : ILLITERATE/SCHOOL/GRADUATE

FOLLOWING SOME QUESTIONS ARE RELATED TO FACTORS AFFECTING MENTAL HEALTH.

PLEASE ANSWER EACH QUESTIONS BY PUTTING (√) MARK IN THE BOX FOLLOWING.

THINKING STYLE RATING SCALE

(SA = STRONGLY AGREE, A= AGREE, N =NEUTRAL, DA=DISAGREE, SDA=STRONGLY DISAGREE)

S. NO	STATEMENTS	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
1.	I FACE THE CHALLENGES OF LIFE WITH CONFIDENCE.					
2.	I FIND HAPPINESS IN HELPING OTHERS.					
3.	MY STUDY ROOM IS CLEANLY BY OTHERS.					
4.	I HELP MY MOTHER IN HOUSE HOLD WORKS.					
5.	I CAN TAKE FAIR MINDED DECISIONS, W HEN I AM CONFUSED.					
6.	I CAN VERY WELL SOLVE THE PROBLEMS OF OTHERS.					
7.	I GOT TIME ONLY TO SOLVE MY OWN PROBLEMS.					
8.	I WILL DO ALL ACTIVITIES WITH SELF MOTIVATIONS.					
9.	I AM AFRAID OF GETTING DEFEATED WHEN I AM TENSED.					
10.	I AM NOT INTERESTED IN HEARING OTHERS SORROWS.					
11.	I HELP MY CLASSMATES WHO ARE FINANCIALLY WEAK.					
12.	I CONSIDER IT IS MY DUTY TO CONSOLE AND VISIT PEOPLE WHO ARE ILL.					
13.	I PARTICIPATE IN GROUP DISCUSSIONS.					
14.	I CALL MY FRIENDS ONLY UNDER DEMANDING CONDITIONS.					
15.	I GIVE IMPORTANCE TO FAMILY RELATIONS THAN OTHERS.					
16.	I CAN DECENTLY RESPOND TO PEOPLE WHEN THEY ARE ANGRY WITH ME.					
17.	I COMPLETE MY WORKS ON TIME.					
18.	I DID NOT STUDY THOSE LESSONS WHICH ARE NOT UNDERSTOOD.					
19.	INCENSE YES/NO ANSWERS ACCORDING TO SITUATIONS.					
20.	I DECIDED TO TAKE MY PRESENT OPTIONAL GROUP AFTER S.S.L.C.					

